

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS.

Sakbaeva Vitaliya

Head of the Uzbek language and literature department
Termez institute of engineering and technology

sakbaevavitavladimirovna@gmail.com

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Annotation

Nowadays pragmatic competence is so important. Lack of pragmatic competence may result to problem in communication such as miscommunication and misunderstanding. The utterances in miscommunication or misunderstanding may be considered rude insults. This is the main reason why students need to learn and to have the pragmatic competence to support their communication abilities. In order to teach that pragmatic competence to students, teacher, then, has to own this competence. He or she has to understand and aware of pragmatics knowledge and pragmatics competence. These issues are discussed in present research.

Key words: psychological component, aware of pragmatics knowledge,

It is also necessary to explain the reason for the absence of the psychological component, which is considered an element of J. Purpura's pragmatic knowledge.

The formation of the components of pragmatic competence is carried out on the basis of training (teaching) a number of pragmatic markers. Pragmatic marker is a lexicon used to express the intended meaning of the language, to organize the discourse and to express the evaluative relationship to the thing (event, concept) being expressed. A sum/set of grammatical and syntactic units is understood. Based on the classification of pragmatic markers proposed by scientist B. Fraser (Fraser B., 1996), four groups of markers can be distinguished: basic/basic (lexical, mixed, syntactic), explanatory, parallel (vocative, protest/dissatisfaction markers) and discursive (contrastive, elaborative, inferential, topic change markers).

The formation of the social component of pragmatic competence is carried out by teaching the use of parallel and explanatory markers.

As a component of communicative competence in a foreign language, the component composition of pragmatic competence was determined, which includes the following elements: a) social component (the ability to interpret social contexts of communication and the social roles of communication participants; the ability to choose a socially acceptable style of communication); b) socio-linguistic (sociolinguistic) component (the ability to interpret speech statements (social meanings, register variations and modality) to create a social image/portrait of the interlocutor)); the ability to use the necessary language and speech tools to achieve the goal of communication in accordance with the selected social roles));

2. It was proposed to look at the formation of the above-mentioned components of pragmatic competence based on teaching pragmatic markers. The formation of the social component of pragmatic competence is carried out by teaching/teaching parallel and explanatory markers. Social cross-activity requires the use of variable means of expression of appeal and evaluation depending on the social context of communication.

3. It is explained by the close relationship of this component of pragmatic competence with socio-cultural competence within the framework of communicative competence in a foreign language. Therefore, the formation of this component is carried out only in conjunction with the formation of socio-cultural competence. Based on its content (variety of genres, cohesion and coherence), the formation of a discourse component involves teaching/learning using a set of relevant discursive markers. Formation of a compensatory component is carried out by using the whole (all) set of pragmatic markers to fill information gaps (deficiencies) in other components.

Pragmatic competence represents the ability to construct statements, combine them into meaning (discourse), knowledge, rules, the ability to use the statement for various communicative functions, the ability to construct statements in a foreign language in accordance with the characteristics of the interaction of communicators and the socio-cultural context. This competence is expressed in the ability to build a statement in accordance with communicative and pragmatic purpose. There are three principles on which pragmatic competence is built. The first of them is the meaning of the expressed thought (thing, event, concept, event). The second principle is the interaction of the interlocutors with each other and the context with them, and the context itself is the third principle.

After determining the place of pragmatic competence in the structure of communicative competence in a foreign language, considering its various models, we should proceed to a detailed study of the components of pragmatic competence itself.

Pragmatic competence is the ability to use language effectively in a contextually appropriate manner. Pragmatic competence is a fundamental aspect of more general communicative competence. Pragmatic competence is understood as knowledge of the linguistic resources available in a given language for the implementation of certain illocutions, knowledge of the sequential aspects of speech acts, and, finally, knowledge of the appropriate contextual use of the linguistic resources of a particular language. And people while interpreting words/sentences add their own intentions to these words/sentences. Thus, words/sentences in their use may change their primary/dictionary meanings. Pragmatics deals with "what people mean by their utterances than what the words or phrases in those utterances might mean by themselves" (Yule, 1996, p.3). Pragmatics mainly deals with what is beyond the dictionary meanings of statements; in other words, it is about what is actually meant with an utterance based on the norms and conventions of a particular society, or context, in which conversation takes place. Therefore, having a good command of the conventions enables the speaker to establish and maintain effective and appropriate communication as well as understanding each other clearly (Yule, 1996) and this ability is generally referred as pragmatic competence (cited in Takkaç Tulgar, A. 2016).

Teaching English to FL students should involve not only familiarizing learners with the sounds, vocabulary, and grammar of the TL, but also helping them to use the TL effectively through making them acquainted with the pragmatic rules that govern the appropriate combination of utterances and communicative functions. And the responsibility

of teaching pragmatic aspects of language use falls on the teachers. However, as language teachers, we face certain challenges. These include lack of adequate materials and training, which are the result of lack of emphasis on pragmatic issues in ESP/EFL teaching methodology.

As we know providing authentic language input is one of the teacher's roles, however, this kind of input is not readily available in the EFL context, and teachers do not have the skills to create pragmatic learning exercises for their learners. Usually, teachers in the FL context do not have frequent contacts with native speakers and therefore, may be unfamiliar with the pragmatic rules of the TL. Consequently, explicit instruction for both teachers and learners seems indispensable.

While thinking on teachability of pragmatics in the ESP context I tried to implement the model suggested by Judd (1999). In this model Judd proposes five steps to be scrupulously followed in order to teach speech acts and develop ESP learners' pragmatic competence. Judd suggests the following steps:

- *Teacher analysis of the speech act:* The aim of this step is to relate the content of what is to be taught with learners' actual needs.
- *Cognitive awareness skills:* At this level learners are exposed to the speech act being taught in order to make them understand the appropriate linguistic realizations that can be employed to express that particular speech act.
- *Controlled productive skills:* It is the stage at which learners are supposed to put into practice the speech act that has been recognized and incorporate it into their pragmatic knowledge.
- *Receptive/integrative skills:* Here, the learners would witness the speech pattern within actual language use as part of discourse rather than in isolation out of context.
- *Free integrated practice:* At this stage learners are supposed not only to produce a particular speech act, but also other forms of language in natural conversation. This last step is considered by Judd (1991) as the real test of learning, since at this point learners should be able to use the speech act appropriately not just in isolation but while engaged in actual communicative interaction.

In simple terms, Pragmatics is about culture, communication, and in the case of second languages, about intercultural communication. In order for second language learners to acquire pragmatic competence, they need to acquire cultural understanding and communication skills.

Furthermore, teaching pragmatic competence is one of the most neglected aspects in English language teaching in most countries where English is taught as a foreign language.

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